

CLARIFYING THE SYNDROME SAVANT

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ABSTRACT

This article addresses the issue of individuals diagnosed with savant syndrome, a very rare type of intellectual manifestation in certain fields of knowledge in which its holder can be considered a prodigy. Its scientific relevance is presented in the sense of provoking a wide and deep discussion on the subject, in which, until the present moment, there is no answer that can clarify its manifestation and what mechanisms can be applied for the conduction of its knowledge in a way to promote real social inclusion. Its social relevance lies in showing that these individuals, in coherent acting situations, could live a normal life and without the excesses that have been placed on them, because of their sui generis conditions. In many cases these extraordinary abilities can be used as a form of social engagement. The disabled person can increase their communication and social interaction skills, promoting the development of everyday life habits and, with this, achieving a certain degree of independence. It is a bibliographical, factual research, based on authors who study the subject and executed with a critical bias, in such a way that it leads to solid arguments. The medical, psychological and pedagogical sciences have not yet been able to present any hypothesis that plausibly clarifies the savant syndrome and its occurrence. In this regard, we argue that the difficulty for this is found in the educational evaluation system, which uses the same and only evaluation instrument, tested and approved in normal individuals, who express themselves through oral language. It turns out that the savant has its own logic, a particular and very unique way of learning. In order to understand him and his mechanisms for absorbing experiences and even how he performs them, it is something that must be found from the observation and the particular study of such individuals, not having the possibility to carry out cross-sectional studies or any other modality that applies to normal individuals.

Keywords: Savant syndrome. Wise idiots. Cerebral hemispheres. Education.

INTRODUCTION

Savant syndrome, known as The wise man's syndrome , idiot-prodigy syndrome or simply *savant* (from the French *savant* , *wise*) is considered a psychic disorder with which the person has a great intellectual ability in contrast to the clinical finding of an intelligence deficit. Such abilities are always linked to an extraordinary memory; however, with little understanding of what is being described. The term *idiot savant* (literally, *wise idiot*) was coined in 1985 and characterizes certain individuals who, despite their cognitive weaknesses, show rare pockets of brilliance in solving certain tasks.

In this sense, Braga and Jorge (2003) clarify that,

Savant Syndrome is not a disorder or a disease in itself. It is, rather, a condition in which extraordinary abilities and prodigious memory are superimposed on an underlying brain dysfunction arising from a developmental defect or mental disorder. Therefore, there is no treatment for Savant Syndrome, other than that aimed at the underlying dysfunction of the central nervous system, such as autism or Asperger's disorder, for example. In cases of people with some other form of central nervous system injury, such as frontotemporal dementia, for example, treatment and rehabilitation would be aimed at those with residual symptoms of such injury (BRAGA & JORGE, 2003, p. 37).

The special talents and abilities that *savants* demonstrate are useful in treating and rehabilitating their underlying disorder or illness. In many cases these extraordinary abilities can be used as a form of social engagement. The disabled person can increase their communication and social interaction skills, promoting the development of everyday life habits and, with this, achieving a certain degree of independence. In this way, special abilities can even serve as *normalization drivers* for the *savant* .

What needs to be clarified is that society admires rare talents, and the presentation of such conditions by some individuals, especially in the fields of the arts, such as Literature, Painting and Music, make them famous, reach stardom, earn legions of fans and admirers; but such an abstract condition does not allow them to have a broad social life, in a normal way; they will always be eccentric individuals in their particularities.

Musical ability is usually the most common to present. Some people with Savant Syndrome can play the piano perfectly without ever having studied to do so. They are able to reproduce songs they heard only once; or, extremely rarely, create your own compositions. The triad mental incapacity, blindness and musical genius was reported with some frequency in the last century. This is a curious fact, particularly considering the relative rarity of each of these

circumstances individually. Talent for the arts, such as painting or drawing, is the second most frequently reported by physicians.

Other forms of artistic talent, such as the ability to make sculptures, may also be present and manifest in individuals who have been diagnosed with *Savant Syndrome*. Calendar calculations (dates) are particularly common among *savants*, especially considering how rare this skill is in the general population. These individuals are able to tell the day of the week on which any given date will occur in a particular year. This ability also includes naming all the years of the next century that Easter will fall on, for example, March 23rd. Furthermore, they also manage to say every year for the next twenty when the 4th of July will be a Tuesday.

Other skills are occasionally seen, including multilingual acquisitions or uncommon languages. Typically one of these skills in particular occurs predominantly in each person with *Savant Syndrome*. However, in some (very rare) cases, multiple abilities can occur in the same person. Whatever the type of ability, it will always be related to a prodigious memory, and it is this type of memory - extraordinarily deep, but at the same time very limited (from a cognitive point of view) - that is present in all the various special abilities. and unites the conditions that characterize the referred syndrome, in question.

Savant Syndrome is a rare condition, in which the person with the most varied mental disorders, including autism, has a brilliant talent or ability that strongly contrasts with their limitations. This condition can be congenital or acquired. Approximately one in ten (10%) autistic people have *Savant Syndrome*. In other forms of mental disorder, retardation or brain injury, *Savant* is present in less than 1% of cases. However, as these other forms of mental illness are much more common than autism, we can say that 50% of people with *Savant Syndrome* are autistic and the other 50% suffer from some other type of disorder, such as failures in development, retardation mental illness or sequelae of brain damage.

What we want to present here is that the term mentally handicapped is a space-time allusion. Possibly, in another situation, in another space-time, in another community, these individuals were considered normal and even worshiped as beloved daughters of the gods, as was the case of several ancient artists who only mastered their particular techniques and did not have broad *ties*. social and that produced memorable works that remain admired until the present day.

The modern school is not prepared to deal with what is strange and bizarre. Since the names of mentally disabled people are historical-social constructions, what is left to define what is and what is not? Therefore, accepting students with disabilities and treating them like a circus attraction is to exclude them from their citizenship and, likewise, to believe that they are divine

miracles, is to subjugate their cognitive abilities. Reading and writing are things that a human being can learn alone, but developing reasoning is not a task that can be done without the help of another. And, that is where the exclusive role of the educator prepared for the exercise of teaching comes into play, which would be to prepare for the critical reflection of the problems that disturb the being in a given historical moment.

According to Morin (2002, p. 7),

The role of education is to teach us to face life's uncertainty; it is to teach us what knowledge is, because they pass us knowledge, but they never tell us what knowledge is. (...) In other words, the role of education is to instruct the spirit to live and face the difficulties of the world.

Education needs to discover how to break with the existing dichotomy between school as a machine for reproducing social inequalities and school as a place par excellence for combating and overcoming these same inequalities. Teaching knowledge is based on the daily practice of their profession and in full clash and dialectic with theory, that is, it is positioned on and from a praxis. In this way, if the objective of the work to be carried out is clear and/or the teacher is committed, then the use of teaching approaches will become more accessible and can guide the entire process.

The current view of the teacher is still mechanistic, and, in order to reflect on how this process occurs and also interferes in the scope of teaching trends, as well as being able to contribute to the delineation of the teacher's identity in this context, an understanding of knowledge is sought and how their knowledge, privileged the reading of some approaches, such as developmental, constructivist, critical-overcoming and systemic, seeking to find subsidy elements to support teachers and to understand what are the pedagogical practices entangled in teaching trends.

The mediation relationships made by the teacher during the pedagogical activities must always be permeated by feelings of welcome, sympathy, respect and appreciation, in addition to understanding, acceptance and appreciation of the other; such feelings not only mark the student's relationship with the object of knowledge, but also affect their self-image, favoring autonomy and strengthening confidence in their capabilities and decisions (SILVA and TASSONI, 2004, p. 17).

From this speech, it is inferred that the pragmatic formation of the child passes through the educators' interest in respecting the particular and diverse worlds that each one brings from their social space. And of your world that is, particularly, yours. In the specific case of *savants*, an entire creative production space needs to be adapted to them, considering their unique

existential condition and that their creative intelligence does not follow the ordinary patterns known and represented by psychology.

The *savant syndrome* is characterized by the fact that individuals who have it present peculiar talents or abilities that, when exposed, are impressive, such as hypermnesia, hyperlexia and hypercalculia, special skills in handling the calendar and different artistic expressions, such as drawing, painting, sculpture and music. Statistically, the prevalence of *savant syndrome* is 1 in 10 people with Autistic Spectrum Disorders and 1 in 1,000 people with brain damage or cognitive impairment (LLOBET, 2019).

SAVANT SYNDROME

This syndrome concerns the condition in which individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorders or intellectual disability have *islands of genius*, that is, highly developed skills in a specific area, which contrasts with their cognitive impairment (Treffert, 2009). The word *savant*, or wise, derives from the French verb to know (*savoir*).

The *savant* is a paradox and, due to his complex condition of intellectual expression, it becomes [*almost*] impossible for him to be able to explain, verbalizing what happens in his psychological world, the neural and mnemonic connections that he executes to arrive at expressing his abilities. In this sense, Young (2001) argues that,

A *Savant* is an individual who demonstrates exceptional ability despite a low level of general functioning. *Savant* syndrome refers to observable behavioral features rather than a diagnostic classification and term; therefore, it incorporates all types of intellectual or mental disability, including autism (Young, 2001, p. 329).

What this author expresses is that the *savant* is still a phenomenon, that is, a figure not understood by the medical sciences and the psychological sciences, in which a diagnosis is linked to an empirical condition of observation and verification of the facts presented in relation to the specific skills expressed. Possibly, one of the difficulties in observing more express cases of *savant manifestation* is the prejudice, especially familiar, that remains in relation to children with specific needs, in which, under a controversial *excess of care* and *overprotection*, they end up preventing them from stopping contact with situations where they could show their exceptional abilities. Added to this, the fact that society has already created a conventionalism about what intelligence is and, in this process, the intellectually gifted, only, by a great occasion,

appear, serving more as a circus attraction than as individuals of right , in which an audience will appreciate your artistic expression.

Savant 's skills generally occur in the following areas: calendar calculation, quick calculations, mathematical ability, arts, music, mechanical skills and spatial skills. Although less common, cases of extraordinary abilities with map memory, visual measurements, extrasensory perception , sharp discrimination of smell or taste, temporal orientation without the use of a watch, among others, have been reported. Typically, the individual has a single skill; however, there are cases in which it presents more than one.

This manifestation of skills that surprise and also delight is linked to the opportunities that are given to those with cognitive limitations, mild or severe. This includes social life itself and environments in which cases could be studied, in particular, and tests applied, access to multivariate didactic resources and waiting for interest in a certain intellect-creative manifestation. We are talking here about a playful work, guided and conducted by a multidisciplinary and multi-scientific team, in which the interest was concentrated on the pragmatic study of the possible artistic or mathematical manifestations of children with specific needs.

A very special condition like this, which was not meant to cause any embarrassment to anyone, could be interpreted by a pseudo humanist as a postmodern segregation mechanism. However, in Cuba, there are special schools, aimed at attending to specific cases and which, in these spaces, knowledge is produced in unquestionable quantity and quality, because the specialist's attention is focused on the case and the individual in question, not having their deviated view to situations outside its investigative scope and, much less negative interference, manifested through anticipated value judgment.

What will make it possible for the *savants* to manifest their skills is the existence of an environment conducive to this, most notably a center where material and, especially, human resources are available, which can help them, from then on, in the development of his manifest abilities, except for the aspect that his intelligence, measured by models and through instruments, known and available until then, put him on the sidelines of any opportunity, because he will not be classified as someone with an intellectual quotient worthy of admiration.

Some authors describe three types of savant syndrome: Savants prodigies, where the autistic individual is unusual in his capacity. Savants with talent, their abilities attract attention due to the disability they have because individuals have autism spectrum disorders. And finally, minutiae savants, that is, they have high wisdom, but limited having a good visual and auditory memory capacity (YUNTA et al., 2003).

This explanation carried out by the authors, mentioned above, in relation to individuals with *savant syndrome*, comes close to an explanation about how they build their internal and external relationships with experience, leading them to learning. Once again, they place us as presenting symptoms of ASD, which would require an accurate diagnosis to clarify whether there is a causal relationship connection or, if they are nothing more than similar aspects, that is, just symptoms that approach each other, not necessarily, characterizing it as a fact.

The model of education that was imposed, as being the ideal, that many accuse as traditional, without presenting the proper criticism and, all the variants that have developed, in an attempt to exalt the ego of pseudo thinkers, did not show itself with minimum conditions of solve the learning problem and, the most conflicting was the impossibility of understanding how the processes of experiences can be transformed into skills, starting with the fact that there is no condition for the realization of empirical situations where the individual can submit his knowledge to the challenge of verifiability and refutability.

In the case of individuals who have *Savant Syndrome*, this condition is even more complex, in all its extension, because the entire process of experience that they carry out is carried out in the most absolute silence of their worlds, always closed to anyone who has not the proper preparation to observe and analyze and understand what is happening and in which dimension. In this sense, what is missing are instruments that can plausibly measure the level of internal and external relationships that they perform, in order to reach the level of skill to be expressed with such power of empirical representation.

To make the interpretation of *Savant*'s thought even more difficult, intelligence assessment instruments are Cartesian, based on objective questions and answers, leaving little or no room for abstraction, in which one could show intellectual capacity through creativity, the which would allow the assessment, with greater propriety, of the relationships between mathematical, mnemonic and literary skills, which, hypothetically, are carried out in different hemispheres of the brain and in specific areas.

Absent a system of evaluation of intellectual capacity, based on experience, in which the individual could express himself within his own logic and not a logic that is imposed on him and, as it does not fit, he ends up receiving a label that is better exemplify your incomprehensible cognitive condition. As a way of minimizing inconsistencies, they evaluate such individuals empirically and then apply the usual tests, as a comparison mechanism with others, and the result creates more confusion than clarification and, in the end, what we have are incomprehensible results from a logical point of view.

It turns out that the *savant* has its own logic, a particular and very unique way of learning. In order to understand him and his mechanisms for absorbing experiences and even how he performs them, it is something that must be found from the observation and the particular study of such individuals, not having the possibility to carry out cross-sectional studies or any other modality that applies to normal individuals.

The anxiety in knowing how the learning processes and symbolic exchanges take place in their respective cognitive worlds proves to be a very high challenge, because the knowledge they demonstrate is, in addition to being very specific, in a dimension of expression that goes beyond common sense and , the social tendency is to equate everyone to the lowest possible level, not the other way around.

Authors who study and publish on the subject are unanimous in stating that *savant syndrome* is a condition of empirical observation, with no way to replicate it in the laboratory, much less how to predict the manifestation of the prodigious condition at any time. Once the case has been detected and the specificity of the action observed, from then on, challenges can be offered to the person with *savant syndrome*, in an attempt to understand the phenomenon and even try to explain it, within the scientific standards that have been established. available, highlighting methodologies, instruments for analyzing and interpreting data, empirical knowledge, previous experiences already recorded.

Quite possibly, with all the advances in the field of neurosciences, using magnetic resonance imaging devices, we will be able to get at least a little closer to knowing which areas of their brains are mobilized when in intellectual activity, be it reproducing something or even creating pragmatic solutions. So far, anything that can be said about the brain functioning of *idiot savants* is nothing more than pure speculation.

According to Treffert (2009), the first mention of the syndrome appeared in an article in a German Psychology magazine, in 1783, which described the case of Jedediah Buxton, a man with extraordinary memory and who made calculations very quickly. In 1887, the first specific description of a *Savant occurred* , by J. Langdon Down (1828-1896) who gave a lecture presenting 10 (ten) cases of people with below average IQ (called idiots at the time) who had fantastic abilities. Based on this situation, in particular, the aforementioned doctor coined the term *Idiot Savant* (*Wise Idiot*) .

Everything that is pointed out about the extreme capacities of these individuals is situated in conditions of performance in abstract areas, contrasting with the inability of not being able to bring this specific action to the field of concreteness, that is, they cannot even explain how they process the data in your thoughts. These prodigies are called idiots, exactly

because they cannot have control over the cognition processes of their respective brains; its capacity for abstraction is null.

For every action that human beings perform, their entire brain is activated and certain parts act with greater intensity; however, there is a whole logical chain that is triggered, linking the empirical action practiced to learning, the mnemonic condition and the process of applying intelligence to the empirical act performed, which is interpreted as creativity; because the individual can elaborate other forms of expression, adding tones, variations, measures, new characters.

From what has been exposed so far, with regard to *savants*, none of this happens, ending the mechanical execution of the act closed in on itself, not being able to explain the mechanisms and procedures that allowed him to execute the musical piece or how to carry out the mathematical operation.

With regard to memory, the same thing happens in that it manages to store certain data and that its mobilization depends on specific commands executed by an external individual. What is meant by this is that they are incapable of writing a text, reporting their phenomenological findings, considering that saying a date, specifically, in relation to any moment in the future, even determining the day of the week that will occur is something, completely out of the ordinary.

Once again, this prodigy will not be able to explain how he arrived at such a result and why he is sure he is not wrong, what methodology he applied so that he could reach the data, with such precision. Nothing that can be taken as a hypothesis proves to be enough to explain the *savant phenomenon* that, by itself, already is and everything that it performs, is much more charming due to this peculiar condition of not being able to be explained exactly.

Empirically, *savants* are incapable of making any logical connection with reality, through the mechanisms, instruments and methodologies that formal education has developed and that the pedagogical sciences have improved up to the present moment. With the scientific advances in the fields of Neurology, in which better instruments are available for visualizing the brain, when excited by didactic, logical and mechanical actions, there is now the possibility of approaching a decipherment of its functioning, when the individual is identified as a *savant*.

From the neurological point of view, his thought can be expressed, as if it were formed by islands that do not connect, in a logical way and, by this expression, let it be understood that it is not given to scientists to know how they are processed; because they are foreign to human behavior, considered as normal.

Apparently, they cannot perform the interpretation of a musical score, being only possible for them to repeat the song itself, from its sound assimilation. This already clarifies that *savants* cannot form logical chains of thought, which already makes it possible to form the hypothesis that the areas of their brain work, empirically; however, they remain isolated, something as if the chains of synapses were not interconnected throughout the brain. Thus examined, “the characteristic of savants can be summarized as intelligence, memory and focus on details, that is, at the level of intelligence, intellectual function was observed as 'average' or 'limited', 'independent' and also 'average'. low” (RODRIGUES, NASCIMENTO and MAIA, 2020, p. 391).

The result of the mechanical action allows them to execute the piece, reproducing it faithfully, because their memory keeps subtle details and, possibly, this condition of not forgetting is the big problem that causes them real disorders. To abstract at the level of learning complex things, in the same dimension as normal individuals, is to demand adaptation to the standard model that society has introduced to everyone and, in the case of *savants*, it will not happen. It may even be that, in their respective private worlds, they wish to be like the others; but, that's not how things work. Their unique nature has endowed them with an existential state in which they feel comfortable in their own closed spaces, living with themselves.

Assessing someone's intelligence, based on the instruments available today, is always a serious risk to take, because the concept of intelligence that is *used* to measure and classify someone is based on Cartesian logic, based on logical reasoning -verbal-mathematical, that is, even if one has mastery over the exact sciences, one must know how to explain the mathematical connections made, decipher formulas and not only know how to perform calculations without the use of paper and pen.

In a society that uses a non-Cartesian evaluation system, it is possible that these individuals would have ample space in common life, coexisting and producing arts, techniques and products with maximum skill; being limited to this condition, without being able to transmit their knowledge, their techniques and their expertise to others.

Until Socrates began his process of destruction of the highest culture known to humanity, the Greek, many of Greece's renowned artists acted and lived like this, isolated from society, in their respective ateliers, producing their works of art and such behavior would never bothered the Greek. After this individual begins his tour of the city of Athens, demanding that the artists know how to express their ways of applying techniques, as if this were a condition of wisdom, the evaluation procedures begin based on the verbalization and linguistic reproduction of the process; leaving the expertise of the technician itself, as a target for the

subjective judgment of individuals who know nothing about the plot and the necessary conditions to reach the production of the artifact.

As a way of understanding the judgment on *savants* applied by the Academy to them, the above example serves well as a starting point to understand the situation. They are all, without exception, much more concerned with *how*, '*how they manage to accomplish such a feat*', rather than appreciating the production presented by such individuals.

For Cartesian science, the *Savant* is, then, the individual who presents an *inconsistent neurological constitution* presenting empirical similarities with some aspects of autism, a well-developed memory, and is in a propitious environment to develop his abilities. As soon as,

My studies suggest that the *Savant* is a neurologically compromised individual with idiosyncratic and divergent intellectual and language ability profiles and intellectual impairments consistent with autism, who has an intense interest in and preoccupation with a particular area of ability. These circumstances, together with the preserved neurological capacity needed to process information in a skill-relevant manner (probably sequential), a well-developed, probably declarative memory, a familial predisposition to high achievement (possibly innate), and adequate support, encouragement and reinforcement, provides the necessary climate for the *Savant* skills to develop (YOUNG, 2001, p. 331).

What the author presents is a generalized picture of the individual who has the *savant syndrome* and ideal conditions that, existing and being applied, directly on himself, could lead him to express his specific capacity and, from this, to perform constant training until that approached empirical excellence in this expressed skill. However, everything that was proposed by Young cannot be translated beyond hypotheses, which, above all, would depend on the empirical manifestation and, how to train someone who may or may not want such a procedure to be carried out?

The impasse posed is that the will of the individual [*even someone with severe cognitive and logical limitations, as is the specific case of savants*] must be sovereign, satisfying his own ego, which can be idiosyncratic and, his free manifestation for Music, Mathematics, Memory needs to be conducted in such a way that their time and their free will are respected; even because you don't know *how* or *why* you feel motivated to express this and that attribute.

The *savant* is a prodigy who cannot have his genius expression process explained by the normal ways that have been defined by contemporary science, exactly, by the fact that he does not interact with the external environment, that is, he does not verbalize and, by not producing this causal link between your internal world and the external world does not allow you to

deduce, with a certain level of security, the internal and external causes that guide and determine the logical connections and interpretations of thought, leading to actions of wide complexity .

The fact that someone does not interact with the external environment does not mean, under any circumstances, that they do not interact with their intrinsic world, and what becomes complex for some scientists and scholars to understand is that knowledge about the other is given to from behavioral observation, the consequent analysis, interpretation and understanding of the attitudes presented and which paths, logical instruments the individual applies to reality until reaching his/her intention. As these individuals, the *savants*, do not express their actions, either because they cannot, or because they themselves do not understand the process by which their respective brains act, everything that happens in their intrinsic worlds remains hypotheses that prove impossible to be empirically tested. .

This situation, in particular, gives rise to many theories that try to explain what, as yet, there is no way to do it, following a logic. Trying to explain a *savant 's capacity for empirical expression* using the logical pattern that has already been determined as an end, to explain high results in normal individuals is to run the risk of falling into a crass error and ending up without clarifying anything about the observed phenomenon.

Pring (2005) mentions three theories that *try* to explain Savantism: extended training, memorization habit and weak coherence. According to Howe et al (as cited in Pring, 2005), it occurs due to an obsession and a lot of practice. Obviously, this model, called extended practice , is not able to explain how these manifestations of talent occur in people who are very young and/or without any training.

Another statement appears here that is difficult to understand, because on what would this *savant obsession manifest itself* ? Being someone who has a limited intelligence, it is strange that he claims to have an interest towards some cognitive aspect, even because such an attitude would require a degree of logical exercise for which the savant individual does not demonstrate the slightest intellectual *capacity* . To say that the environment can be the creator of a motivational condition and that, given the repetition of the situation, it assimilates it, until it becomes possible to accept it as *possible*, not as a fact.

To the same extent, talking about constant practice is another statement that proves to be without logical foundations, because the attention of normal human beings is determined by their age, and every predetermined period of time this is highlighted, so that it is not lost. the focus. Furthermore, obsession is a feeling that affects prodigies with a high IQ, with a logical demonstration of their effort towards a pre-defined objective. There is a whole verbalization in

the sense of dominating the particular interest, something not observed in the behavior of *savants*.

Taking all these explanations about the limits that the infra-gifted present in their respective behaviors, the claim that the genius of a *savant* is a product of excessive and obsessive training is falling into contradiction with the intellectual situation presented by them, with regard to the everyday practical activity. Nothing can prove, on the contrary, that living in a rich environment cannot represent a motivator capable of enhancing areas that are already very strong in these children.

If, by chance, you take one of these children tutored by a health agent who has domains in the fields of Pedagogy, it is quite possible that you can create a discipline of studies, training and formatting of thought that leads you to a particular type of excellence in a given cognitive field that has already demonstrated superior skills and that are capable of impressing with their quality and technical resourcefulness.

Thinking of any other possibility outside this very restricted context, *savants* remain as rare manifestations of super gifted individuals who do extraordinary things that nobody can explain, in a plausible and objective way. All initiatives to explain facts and phenomena that are far from being clarified through the tools and knowledge currently available on brain functioning have become commonplace. *Deductions* have been taken as *scientific findings* that, in a short time, become absolute, unquestionable truths, without holding factual evidence about what happened.

For the manifestation of the *savant* phenomenon, an entire exceptional conjuncture of situations and opportunities must be available, highlighting the professionals involved who must be duly prepared to act in situations that are beyond the ordinary and who have an accurate capacity for the scientific observation of phenomena outside of the curve. Until a certain phenomenon is capable of being explained, it is a peaceful object to be exposed to the academic-scientific world as an observed and registered empirical manifestation. From then on, everyone is free to present their preliminary hypotheses and discussions about the phenomenon described, without this ending the discussion or, in the absence of objective answers, the case being taken as impossible to be solved, interpreted and/or explained. The *Savant individual* is an incomprehensible phenomenon by itself and what is known as data is not enough to reach conclusions about his intellectual potential and logical manifestation of his abilities, precisely because it is not possible to replicate his abilities, given that it is unknown how its cerebral system works and, more specifically, its memory.

In this sense, Treffert (1988 *apud* REILY, 2001, p. 571) points out that,

Memory formation, consolidation, and retrieval require differential involvement of the hippocampus, amygdala, and thalamus. The *Savant*'s memory, so deep yet so narrow, so vast yet so lacking in emotion, so limitless yet so rigid, certainly uses a different circuitry than ordinary memory, which is much shallower but extremely broad, less vast but charged with emotions, and more limited but flexible, associative and creative.

The author makes an interesting game of brain functions linked to memory and, in the case of *savant individuals*, he presents his hypothesis that there is no direct connection between the corresponding areas of the brain, especially with regard to the production of affective ties. It is a known fact that mnemonic mobilization is directly linked to feelings, sensitivity. In this case, the primordial element is the impossibility for the limbic system to connect to other brain territories.

Llobet (2019) presents the hypothesis about the disability that individuals with *savant syndrome* have in the left hemisphere of the brain. Also known as holistic or dominant, he is responsible for intellectual activities, critical sense, logical reasoning; the right side of the brain is linked to creativity by musical, artistic and intuitive sense. Both sides are connected by a structure called the corpus callosum formed by several bundles of nerve fibers that unite the two sides of the brain, in the expectation that they can work together. It is for this fact that savantism is also known as *idiot savant*, which means *wise idiot*, precisely because of the logical inability to use the left hemisphere at the same time that it has an endowment on the right.

This hypothesis of dominant lateralization of the brain, in which one works and the other does not, comes close to a very convincing justification for the occurrence of savantism; however, it needs to be better elucidated and even empirically proven, because it does not account for clarifying the fluent domain of *savants* in specific areas, despite training and complex elaborations of logical connections of thought.

What most draws attention is the *savants' lack of connectivity* with the external world, which does not mean, under any circumstances, that there is no internal connectivity; it is just not possible to understand how it occurs, due to the fact that there is no verbalization by the individual himself about its occurrence and interaction. In normal individuals, memory is activated through countless factors, such as smells, objects, situations, always making intercurrent connections in such a way that, in the end, there is a path that can be described in a logical way. As far as it is possible to deduce, in individuals with *savant syndrome*, it is not possible to say precisely if such internal and external connections happen and how they happen.

As far as human thought and its functions are known, it is known that they exist; however, explaining them is what becomes a very difficult task.

savant 's knowledge is not evident in his memory, but in his production". It is worth mentioning that we are not talking about knowledge, but about *knowledge*, because there is no abstract mastery of a technique, with a representation of a certain piece of music or the mathematical execution of processes, as well as the definition of future dates, which does not that is to say, it represents any logical domain of memory, just the direct result of calculations performed very precisely.

The great challenge is how this individual stores the information necessary to carry out the mathematical calculations and how he mobilizes them in order to find the results with such accuracy. As a rule, these geniuses are considered *idiots* precisely because they cannot explain these occurrences that enchant those who watch them; but which, at the same time, cannot replicate the intelligence conditions they present. One can come to understand that the fact that they are so called is more due to a feeling of anger and hatred towards scientists, in which they take them as selfish creatures who do not share their superior knowledge out of pure narcissism.

It must always be clear that the conditions of knowledge about the functioning of the human brain over which we have mastered so far, in addition to being based on deductions, are guided by observations and mediated by language. Therefore, those who do not speak, do not express themselves verbally, as is the case with *savants* , making the deduction of the phenomena that occurred a little more complex and far from a plausible understanding, which gives rise to the most intriguing hypotheses that do not hold.

Savants present themselves are not usual, that is, the observations are always about an individual and not about a group and, no matter how hard one tries, those who present the savant syndrome *are*, categorically, shy, introverted and their presentations are reserved for circumspect groups, even so there is no guarantee that they would be comfortable expressing their potential.

All that is observed, in relation to individuals with *savant syndrome*, is that there is a desperate attempt to explain what happens and, this situation, in particular, is ridiculous, because the phenomenon is observable, it is public and notorious; what challenges is the *how*; how such a situation becomes external, since the internalization of the learning acquisition process did not follow the ordinary customary ritual that applies to all individuals and, this is where it comes close to understanding that the Savant is not someone normal , not from the cognitive point of view, which can be analyzed and its ability to express intelligence,

highlighting, Creativity can be measured through the simple tools that Pedagogy, Psychology and Medicine currently have.

Even if instruments and techniques were available, of high and extreme sophistication, the problem of analysis and understanding of the manifest behavior of *savants* would represent a problem, because the professionals involved in the examination would have to be many levels above the average to interpret the collected data, empirically, not being subject to the issuance of hurried hypotheses, in order to obtain answers from impatient onlookers.

Even with all the technological apparatus available on the market, which has greatly helped scholars in the field of neurology, the challenge lies in the fact that the human species bases its analysis on language and, despite the fact that the interpretation is always from the other; the expression only has merit value if given by the patient himself. The great difficulty of verbal expression of these individuals; sometimes, even, almost, non-existent, prevents logical explanatory results about how their brains work, how they learn, how they store the set of information they receive from the environment and, in particular, how they relate the internal and external causes of their existence, transforming them into conditions of cognitive expression.

There is a consensus among medical specialists that, to date, there is no theory that can shed light on the intellectual and mnemonic processes of *savants*, leaving open the challenges to be answered. Siqueira et al. says,

At the moment, there is no medical theory that can explain the reason for this curious human condition, at least not in its entirety. Although some have obvious savant brain damage, in others it is not possible to find any trace of 'abnormality', at least not by current diagnostic tools (SIQUEIRA, GALVÃO, MARQUES JÚNIOR and REUSE, 2021, p. 6).

The fact that there is still no medical theory that can explain a certain phenomenon, in the case, in question, about *savants* and their respective manifest behaviors, this does not classify them as creatures beyond the reach of science; it only reveals that the investigation methods used, still, do not even manage to approach a plausible deduction and that sustains itself as a theoretical argument.

Llobet (2019), based on the knowledge that we have, so far, of the functioning of the brain of normal individuals, ventures to argue that the causes of *savant syndrome* are diverse. In his conception, he immediately presents three hypotheses: 1. In principle, *savant individuals* suffer from a developmental disorder; 2. Suffer from an autism spectrum disorder; or, 3. Suffer from some type of brain damage in the left cerebral hemisphere. There is still no general

agreement as to the cause of *savant syndrome*. The main hypothesis is that damage to the left hemisphere causes the right hemisphere to have more development to compensate. This imbalance. Additionally, most people with *savant syndrome* also have an Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). One of the symptoms of ASD is having narrow interests, which may be the reason for developing a particular skill exceptionally.

Associating *Savant Syndrome* with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) seems to be another way of being able to explain something, so far, without logical explanation, through a shortcut, instead of carrying out particular studies on the phenomenological manifestation of the fact. Attempting an explanation through innatism²⁵ is an act of desperation, at the risk of being ridiculed by fellow scientists, whoever dares to do so.

The fact is that, at some point, the *savant* has contact with didactic experience situations that induce him to learn things that his brain processes with great ease and speed, surprising those around him, because the skills presented in areas specific, notably those where the majority of the population has certain difficulties, such as memory, mathematics, complex calculations, future dates.

What can be suggested, as a question would be: considering that in individuals, in general, language and communication are determining factors, to what extent would these specific domains affect the development of skills in the field of hard sciences, the so-called exact sciences? And, as *savant* individuals do not demonstrate mastery in this field, would this open up opportunities for these numerical forms of expression to be a communication mechanism with the outside world? A kind of relationship between internal and external causes linked to cognition?

This hypothesis would go against what Llobet (2019) defended, as an idea, that there would be a difficulty in interconnection between the cerebral hemispheres, if we take as an accepted hypothesis, the idea that, being the left side of the brain more mathematical and the transformation, the decoding of this complex language would take place on the right side of the brain, which would take care of making it comprehensible to everyone, therefore, logical, understanding the term in the sense of being adapted to the environment in which it is inserted. In this sense, the explanation that comes closest to an actual clarification is that the right side

²⁵ *Innatism* is the theory that defends the existence of ideas, capacities or attitudes that are born with man, without the need for experience or learning to be acquired. Plato (843-763 AH) presents this idea, defended by Socrates (885-814 AH), in his dialogue *Menón*. In this book, Plato investigates the nature of knowledge, arguing that the mind, or soul, has traversed many lifetimes, both inside and outside bodies. Knowledge consists in remembering these past experiences (NA, 2023).

of the brain would not be able to decode the messages that would reach it, coming from the left side.

Savant cases show exceptional levels of talent in the arts, in memory; however, these individuals suffer from creativity, that is, according to some authors, they do not have abstract thinking (GARCÍA et al., 2011). Thus, a *savant* is an individual who demonstrates exceptional ability despite a low level of general functioning. The expression *Savant Syndrome* refers to observable behavioral characteristics rather than a diagnostic classification and the term therefore incorporates all types of intellectual or mental disability, including autism (CASTILHO, 2011).

Again, there is the question of the impossibility of creation that is given to the individual who has the *Savant Syndrome*, as this was a limiting element, due to the simple fact that he has cognitive limitations diagnosed through a binary Cartesian system. The dogmatism with which they are judged already determines their incapacities in the face of a society that has defined its own models of being and existing, and everything that does not fit this pre-molded profile is subjected to a condition of undervalue, and must be excluded from social life. wide and, prevented from daring to create, since it has been determined that it is incapable of doing so.

When an evaluation model is applied that tries to make everyone equal, *the forceps*, the result is a society where everyone, indistinctly, is classified by the average; translated into contemporary terms, they are all the same. Those individuals who do not fit into such an atomic model of society end up as *aberrations*; because their behaviors are indecipherable by the didactic instruments that train professionals who are considered able, from a legal point of view, to determine them in this way.

What is needed is the development of an empirical tool that is able to analyze the intelligence of the individual *Savant* and explain how the neural, synaptic connections in their brain occur, clarifying a little more about the functioning of the human brain, as a whole. This demands direct investments in the training of professionals who are willing to search a space in the brain, until then, little known about how it works, how it responds to stimuli from the external environment and processes them internally.

The intelligence of *savants* can only be measured through direct empirical observation. For this, it is necessary to use professionals from different branches of scientific and academic knowledge, so that hypotheses can be produced that prove to be plausible and that have the strength to open paths for more incisive investigations on the subject and on the functioning of the human brain. .

The in-depth study of *savants* is an opportunity to learn how the procedures for absorbing and processing information, as well as the transformation of these into knowledge, are processed through thought and how this proves to be possible to be replicated in other more or less complex situations. of learning. This requires high investments in research and development, both in methodological resources and in human resources, especially in terms of data collection and observation of empirical learning situations.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Savant Syndrome represents a very intense challenge for the areas of medical, psychological and pedagogical sciences, because each of them seeks an answer closer to understanding its occurrence, definition and presentation of symptoms, as well as the use of empirical and theoretical practices. of learning that help such individuals to insert themselves in society with greater power of autonomy.

The difficulties encountered in relation to savant individuals are in the interpretation of their respective intellectual capacities presented, empirically, without being able to express the mechanisms they adopt to reach such a level of knowledge, without apparent training and without demonstrating conditions of neural interrelationships. between the cerebral hemispheres.

In the field of medical sciences, the difficulties are in explaining how individuals with an apparent low level of intellectual capacity, classified as idiots (IQ<40) can perform actions that, in the current understanding and understanding, in consonance with the current molds of analysis and evaluation, could only be performed by individuals considered geniuses. The challenge is to know how the different brain areas communicate, making the information received processed at the level of the cerebral hemisphere.

In the field of psychological sciences, the challenge is to understand how the procedures for receiving and processing information take place, transforming them into useful knowledge and learning. How cognitive processes occur, relating the internal and external causes of the message coming from the environment.

In the field of pedagogical sciences, the challenge is even greater, because how to apply a didactics based on stereotyped models, which is based on a model of evaluation of knowledge, solely on the memoristic condition and repetition of what, supposedly, was learned for hours exhaustive readings and obsolete discourses, to evaluate someone who is unable to explain how things are processed and connected in their intrinsic world?

Finally, we present our hypothesis that, the individual who is diagnosed with *savant syndrome* has a broad capacity for information storage and cognitive processing, with difficulty in elaborating functions of the right and left hemispheres of the brain, which makes them most of their creativity, which is defended by Dau (2023), as the manifestation of intelligence, is elaborated in the left hemisphere, which uses a mathematical, symbolic language and, failing to process these in the right hemisphere, which has an articulated language, interpreted and clarified more along the lines of human social communication and, based on this impossibility, this individual expresses himself as he is able to do so. Therefore, it is the interpretation mechanisms of their expressed language that are not able to understand them and what they produce.

Possibly, in a pragmatic society that adopted empirical evaluation mechanisms and was less concerned with trying to understand what is beyond their cognitive reach, these individuals would pass as normal people, endowed with superior talents and produce works and products useful to society.

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